
Non-Archimedean Tarski-Maligranda Inequalities

K. Mahesh Krishna

School of Mathematics and Natural Sciences

Chanakya University Global Campus

NH-648, Haraluru Village

Devanahalli Taluk, Bengaluru North District

Karnataka State, 562 110, India

Email: kmaheshak@gmail.com

Date: January 20, 2026

Abstract: In 1930, Tarski observed that

$$||r| - |s|| = |r - s| + |r + s| - (|r| + |s|), \quad \forall r, s \in \mathbb{R}.$$

In 2008, Maligranda converted the previous equality into inequalities that are valid in every normed linear space. We derive non-Archimedean versions of Tarski-Maligranda inequalities. Difference between Archimedean and non-Archimedean inequalities is surprising.

Keywords: Normed linear space, Non-Archimedean linear space.

Mathematics Subject Classification (2020): 12J25, 46S10.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is universally known that

$$(1) \quad ||r| - |s|| \leq \min\{|r - s|, |r + s|\}, \quad \forall r, s \in \mathbb{R}.$$

In 1930, Tarski noticed a strengthening of Inequality (1) (Page 688, [4]):

$$(2) \quad ||r| - |s|| = |r - s| + |r + s| - (|r| + |s|), \quad \forall r, s \in \mathbb{R}.$$

It is easy to see that Equality (2) fails for complex numbers. In 2008, Maligranda showed that one can generalize Equality (2) by deriving inequalities that hold for any normed linear space (NLS) [1].

Theorem 1.1. [1] (*Tarski-Maligranda Inequalities*) Let \mathcal{X} be a NLS. Then for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$,

$$(3) \quad ||\|x\| - \|y\|| \leq \|x + y\| + \|x - y\| - (\|x\| + \|y\|) \leq \min\{\|x - y\|, \|x + y\|\}$$

and

$$(4) \quad ||\|x\| - \|y\|| \leq \|x\| + \|y\| - \|\|x + y\| - \|x - y\|\|.$$

We naturally seek non-Archimedean versions of Inequalities (3) and (4). In this note, we derive them.

2. NON-ARCHIMEDEAN TARSKI-MALIGRANDA INEQUALITIES

Let \mathbb{K} be a field. A map $|\cdot| : \mathbb{K} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is said to be a non-Archimedean valuation if following conditions hold.

- (i) If $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}$ is such that $|\lambda| = 0$, then $\lambda = 0$.
- (ii) $|\lambda\mu| = |\lambda||\mu|$ for all $\lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{K}$.

(iii) (Ultra-triangle inequality) $|\lambda + \mu| \leq \max\{|\lambda|, |\mu|\}$ for all $\lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{K}$.

In this case, \mathbb{K} is called as non-Archimedean valued field [3]. Let \mathcal{X} be a vector space over a non-Archimedean valued field \mathbb{K} with valuation $|\cdot|$. A map $\|\cdot\| : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is said to be a non-Archimedean norm if following conditions hold.

- (i) If $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is such that $\|x\| = 0$, then $x = 0$.
- (ii) $\|\lambda x\| = |\lambda| \|x\|$ for all $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}$, for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$.
- (iii) (Ultra-norm inequality) $\|x + y\| \leq \max\{\|x\|, \|y\|\}$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

In this case, \mathcal{X} is called as non-Archimedean linear space (NALS) [2]. Following is non-Archimedean version of Theorem 1.1.

Theorem 2.1. (*Non-Archimedean Tarski-Maligranda Inequalities*) *Let \mathcal{X} be a NALS. Then for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$,*

$$\left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| \leq \frac{2}{|2|} \max\{\|x - y\|, \|x + y\|\} - (\|x\| + \|y\|) \leq \frac{2}{|2|} \max\{\|x\|, \|y\|\} - (\|x\| + \|y\|)$$

and

$$\left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| \leq \|x\| + \|y\| - \frac{2}{|2|} \left| \|x + y\| - \|x - y\| \right|.$$

In particular, if $|2| = 1$, then

$$\left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| \leq 2 \max\{\|x - y\|, \|x + y\|\} - (\|x\| + \|y\|) \leq 2 \max\{\|x\|, \|y\|\} - (\|x\| + \|y\|)$$

and

$$\left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| \leq \|x\| + \|y\| - 2 \left| \|x + y\| - \|x - y\| \right|.$$

Proof. Let $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$. Then

$$(5) \quad \|x\| + \|y\| + \left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| = 2 \max\{\|x\|, \|y\|\}.$$

We also have

$$(6) \quad \max\{\|x - y\|, \|x + y\|\} \geq \|(x + y) + (x - y)\| = \|2x\| = |2| \|x\|$$

and

$$(7) \quad \max\{\|x - y\|, \|x + y\|\} \geq \|(x + y) - (x - y)\| = \|2y\| = |2| \|y\|.$$

Inequalities (6) and (7) give

$$(8) \quad \max\{\|x - y\|, \|x + y\|\} \geq |2| \max\{\|x\|, \|y\|\}.$$

Inequalities (5) and (8) give

$$\|x\| + \|y\| + \left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| = 2 \max\{\|x\|, \|y\|\} \leq \frac{2}{|2|} \max\{\|x - y\|, \|x + y\|\}.$$

Rearranging,

$$\left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| \leq \frac{2}{|2|} \max\{\|x - y\|, \|x + y\|\} - (\|x\| + \|y\|).$$

We next see that

$$(9) \quad \|x\| + \|y\| - \left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| = 2 \min\{\|x\|, \|y\|\}.$$

Further,

$$(10) \quad \left| \|x + y\| - \|x - y\| \right| \leq \|(x + y) + (x - y)\| = \|2x\| = |2|\|x\|$$

and

$$(11) \quad \left| \|x + y\| - \|x - y\| \right| \leq \|(x + y) - (x - y)\| = \|2y\| = |2|\|y\|.$$

Inequalities (10) and (11) give

$$(12) \quad \left| \|x + y\| - \|x - y\| \right| \leq |2| \min\{\|x\|, \|y\|\}.$$

Inequalities (9) and (12) give

$$\left| \|x + y\| - \|x - y\| \right| \leq |2| \min\{\|x\|, \|y\|\} = \frac{|2|}{2} (\|x\| + \|y\| - \left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right|).$$

Rearranging,

$$\left| \|x\| - \|y\| \right| \leq \|x\| + \|y\| - \frac{2}{|2|} \left| \|x + y\| - \|x - y\| \right|.$$

□

3. CONCLUSIONS

- (1) In 1930, Tarski observed an equality in triangle inequality for real numbers.
- (2) In 2008, Maligranda converted equality by Tarski to inequalities which are valid in every normed linear spaces.
- (3) In this note, we derived non-Archimedean version of Tarski-Maligranda inequalities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lech Maligranda. Some remarks on the triangle inequality for norms. *Banach J. Math. Anal.*, 2(2):31–41, 2008.
- [2] C. Perez-Garcia and W. H. Schikhof. *Locally convex spaces over non-Archimedean valued fields*, volume 119 of *Camb. Stud. Adv. Math.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [3] W. H. Schikhof. *Ultrametric calculus. An introduction to p-adic analysis*, volume 4 of *Camb. Stud. Adv. Math.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006.
- [4] Alfred Tarski. *Collected papers. Volume 4: 1958–1979*. Cham: Birkhäuser, 2019.